

SZ-plugin: a space-time data-driven modeler in QGIS

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¹**Abstract** — Geospatial operators frequently use GIS platforms for managing databases and pre-processing data, but advanced data-driven analyses are usually performed outside these systems. The original SZ-plugin (version 1.0) attempted to address this by integrating modeling tools into QGIS. However, its capabilities were limited to binary classifications. In this work we present the latest version of the SZ-plugin (2.0) which introduces three key advancements: (1) an extension for space-time analysis (2), the inclusion of the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) and (3) the relative regression GAM and MLP models in addition to the previous data-driven classifiers. The plugin has been tested in Taiwan for landslide prediction but it is versatile and applicable across various geospatial fields.

I. INTRODUCTION

The SZ-plugin is a tool for QGIS that integrates data-driven models for geospatial analysis. In this work we present the second version of the plugin (2.0). The first version of the plugin published in Titti et al. (2022) was limited to binary classifiers for spatial problems, which restricted its ability to model dynamic processes. The updated version introduces three major enhancements: a space-time extension, new classifiers such as Generalized Additive Models (GAMs) and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) and regression options. With these additions, users can now estimate both susceptibility, using classifiers, (Steger et al., 2024; Ahmed et al., 2023) and intensity, using regressors, (Lombardo et al., 2021) over time. This broadens the applicability beyond landslide prediction to include digital soil mapping, wildfire susceptibility, land-use classification and more.

The enhanced SZ-plugin has been tested in Taiwan (Figure 1). The dataset used for testing spans 14 years (2004–2018) and has been partitioned in 64,5036 slope units (SUs) (Alvioli et al., 2016),

Figure 1: Cumulated landslide extension from 2004 to 2018 in Taiwan (modified from Titti et al., 2025).

enabling comprehensive space-time analysis. First published by Fang et al. (2024), the dataset includes a range of geo-environmental variables. It is organized on a yearly basis, with the cumulative landslide area for each year recorded within each SU. The landslides considered in this study are classified as shallow debris slides and flows.

This work illustrates the core functionalities of the SZ-plugin by comparing the results of classification and regression analysis based on GAM and MLP algorithms to predict landslides susceptibility, based on the landslide presence/absence, and the relative landslide extension in space and time, respectively.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The SZ-plugin supports three groups of models: 1) Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine and Random Forest, adapted from the previous version, have been optimized for space-time modeling; 2) GAM, which allows for flexible, nonlinear relationships between predictors and response variables; 3) MLP, a deep learning architecture that captures complex interactions among variables for both classification and regression tasks. The Graphical User Interface of the tool is visible in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Graphical User Interface of the SZ-plugin

The inclusion of GAMs enables the modeling of both binomial likelihoods (for susceptibility estimation) and Gaussian likelihoods (for intensity prediction). The MLP model offers an alternative data-driven approach for users looking to leverage neural networks for geospatial predictions. Two branches of the MLP have been implemented, one to model regression (for intensity prediction) and the other to model classification (for susceptibility estimation). Moreover, an additional block of functions has been integrated to the new SZ version allowing users to transfer knowledge across space and/or time based on the data-driven algorithms described before.

To ensure robustness, the SZ-plugin provides a number of performance metrics for evaluating model prediction capacity. The classification metrics include: Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the

ROC curve, F1-score (F1) and Cohen’s Kappa (K). Concerning the regression metrics, have been implemented: Root Mean Square Error, Mean Absolute Error, Mean Absolute Percentage Value, R^2 and Pearson Correlation Coefficient.

To validate the model performance, the SZ-plugin supports various cross-validation methods: random clustering, spatial clustering which uses k-means to partition, temporal validation with different time combinations, and spatiotemporal validation which integrates both spatial and temporal domains.

All the analysis has been conducted selecting 8 covariates from the original Taiwanese dataset: northness (NorthM), eastness, slope (SlopeM), plan curvature, profile curvature, maximum daily rain in the year (RainM), mean NDVI in the year (NDVIm), lithology (litho). The largest lithology class presents per SU has been selected (Figure 3).

A space-time analysis requires at least the selection of one dynamic covariate which evolves in the time window considered. Thus, we selected the NDVIm and RainM as dynamic factors, the other covariates as static in the 14 years considered.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overall, 6 analyses have been conducted: binomial GAM and MLP classifier for susceptibility estimation in the range 2004-2018, Gaussian GAM and MLP regressor for intensity estimation between 2004 and 2018, and finally the relative predictions in 2019.

The main difference between statistical models and neural networks is the ability to interpret the results. GAMs regression coefficients allow the user to understand the contribution of each covariate to the final probability, while this is not possible with the MLP model in both regression and classification modes. Figure 3 shows examples of regression coefficients patterns of a linear, ordinal and categorical variable of binomial and Gaussian GAMs.

Although the results of the MLP algorithm are not easily interpretable, its predictive performance surpasses that of the statistical models. Figure 4 shows a comparison of the validation metrics for the GAM and MLP classifications running a space-time cross-validation.

Finally, the prediction has been conducted collecting, out of the dataset published by Fang et al. (2024), the 2019 NDVIm and RainM. Then, the model trained from 2004 to 2018 has been transferred to the subsequent time domain. The susceptibility and intensity maps based on GAM and MLP are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 3: Selection of the GAM partial effects resulting from the binomial and gaussian models from 2004 to 2018 (modified from Titti et al., 2025). Each class is identified by an identification number from 0 to 14: 0) alluvium, 1) andesite, basalt, and serpentine, 2) metamorphic limestone, 3) black schist, green schist, and sandy schist, 4) laterite, gravel, sand and clay, 5) mudstone intercalated with allochthonous, 6) gneiss, 7) hard shale and sandstone, 8) agglomerate and tuffaceous sandstone, 9) sandstone, mudstone, and shale, 10) phyllite, slate, and sandstone, 11) sandstone, shale, and coaly shale, 12) quartzite, slate, and coaly shale, 13) shale, siltstone, and sandstone, 14) hard shale, slate, and phyllite.

Figure 4: Space-time cross-validation metrics of GAM and MLP classifiers from 2004 to 2018 (modified from Titti et al., 2025).

The integration of space-time models into GIS software marks a substantial advancement in geospatial analysis. The SZ-plugin eliminates the inefficiencies associated with transferring data between multiple platforms, enabling a more streamlined and

Figure 5: GAM and MLP-based susceptibility and intensity predictive maps, in the year 2019 (modified from Titti et al., 2025).

efficient workflow. Its flexibility allows applications beyond landslide studies, including wildfire risk assessment, flood forecasting, and more. Despite its advantages, the plugin has some computational limitations, particularly related to the Python *pygam* package (Serven and Brummitt, 2018) used to build the GAMs module and to the *scikit-learn* package (Pedregosa et al., 2011) used to build the MLP module of the SZ-plugin. The former lacks multi-core processing capabilities, limiting scalability for large datasets. The latter runs on the CPU rather than on the GPU used by the most powerful packages for neural networks. Therefore, future improvements may focus on optimizing computational efficiency through parallel processing.

Another potential enhancement involves integrating deep learning frameworks, such as transformer neural networks (Dahal et al., 2024), to further improve prediction accuracy in modeling complex spatiotemporal relationships.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The SZ-plugin enables users to handle classification and regression tasks across spatial and temporal domains, eliminating the need for extensive input/output operations. It streamlines the analytical process, making advanced modeling techniques more accessible to a broader audience.

Furthermore, the ability to transfer in space, but more significantly, in time the trained knowledge, enhances susceptibility modeling and supports a wide range of new applications based on predictions.

The SZ-plugin is available on the official QGIS plugin repository (plugins.qgis.org/plugins/sz_module) and on GitHub (github.com/SZtools/SZ-plugin), ensuring accessibility for researchers and practitioners worldwide. The documentation is available at the following website: sz-docs.readthedocs.io.

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